

Agro2Circular

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D1.1 – A2C REQUIREMENTS

November 2023

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Technical references

Project Acronym	Agro2Circular
Project Title	TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR
Project Coordinator	Fuensanta Monzo CETEC fuensanta.monzo@agro2circular.org
Project Duration	October 2021 – September 2024 (36 months)

Deliverable No.	D1.0
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 1- A2C Specifications, Residues Management and Data Integration System
Task	T1.1 - Requirements
Lead beneficiary	CETEC
Contributing beneficiary/ies	2(GWC) 4(IRIS) 8(UNIMIB) 9(UA) 13(CTNC) 14(MCT) 15(ALM) 16(PROEXP) 17(DMC) 18(CITROMIL SL) 33(ECO) 34(EQU) 35 (EXUS) 36(EVRY) 37 (SOLP) 38 (EVER) 39(LoL)
Due date of deliverable	31Dec2021
Actual submission date	31Dec2021

* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

V	Date	Comments
v0.1	09/12/2021	First draft of document
v0.2	13/12/2021	Revised version based on the comments of the coordinator, SOL and EVER
v1.0	28/12/2021	First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.
v1.1	23/11/2023	First draft based upon first final version
v2.0	24/11/2023	Second final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Document Distribution Log

Version	Date	Distributed to
v0.1	13/12/2023	The coordinator, SOLP, EVER, CTNC
v0.2	15/12/2023	CETEC
V1.1	24/11/2023	Coordinator

Verification and approval

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	Jaime Ortíz	26/11/2023
Approval Final Deliverable by coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó	26/11/2023

Disclaimer and acknowledgement

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List of abbreviations

FCM: Food contact materials.

MD: Machine Directions.

OTR: Oxygen transmission rate.

PET: Polyethylene terephthalate.

TD: Transverse Directions.

WVTR: Water vapour transmission rate.

OECD The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.

MTC Mass Transfer Coefficient.

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1. Project description.

Agro2Circular aims to develop two value chains for the upcycling of two types of agrifood industrial waste; fruit & vegetable waste and plastic waste, generated by the agrifood industry in the Region of Murcia, Spain.

As a starting point of the project, the technical specifications of all the products that are going to be developed during the A2C project have been collected in this deliverable: technical requirements of food formulations, nutraceuticals, formulations, cosmetic formulations, plastic and bioplastic compounds specifications, agricultural films and food packaging characteristics and the Data Integration System characteristics.

During the project, new food, nutraceutical (demonstrators 3 and 4) and cosmetic formulations (demonstrators 2, 3, 4 and 5) will be developed using the bio-actives obtained from fruit & vegetable waste through 2 extractions routes to be developed. New cosmetic formulations will also be prepared from building blocks and natural carotenoids obtained through bio-processes developed for the upcycling of agri-food plastic waste and fruit waste. In the case of new food and nutraceutical formulations, CITROMIL will produce a fibre-enriched lemon juice, a flavonoid-enriched lemon juice and a lemon fibre extract, AGROTRANSFORMADOS will produce a fruit juice enriched with fibre, a fruit juice enriched with citrus extract and a compote/purée enriched with fibre. ALMOND will produce two fibre-enriched almond desserts. DOMCA will produce a nutraceutical antioxidant. LoLo Bio Cosmetics will produce a moisturising body cream with antioxidants.

In the case of plastic products, EVERSIA will produce biodegradable food packaging and food packaging made of recycled plastic and SOLPLAST biodegradable agricultural films and agricultural films made of recycled plastic, all with gas barrier properties.

The Data Integration System will be a tool to ensure the traceability of all materials involved in Agro2Circular value chains and to support the optimisation of the processes thanks to Big Data and Machine Learning technologies.

The datasheets for all the products to be produced are included in ANNEX I.

These new formulations and plastic products have to comply with the technical-sanitary requirements.

2. Technical specifications

2.1 New food formulations characteristics.

The growing of fruit and vegetables produces a huge amount of waste not only in their farming but also along the supply chain. The A2C project represents a step towards making use of this waste by manufacturing new products from the natural bio-actives obtained from the waste. These new food formulations have to meet the following regulations:

NEW FOOD FORMULATIONS

ENRICHED JUICES

- **DIRECTIVE 2012/12/EU** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 April 2012 amending Council Directive 2001/112/EC on fruit juices and other similar products intended for human consumption.
- **COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) No 1040/2014** of 25 July 2014 amending Council Directive 2001/112/EC relating to fruit juices and certain similar products intended for human consumption to adapt its Annex I to technical progress.
- **REGULATION (EC) No 1925/2006** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 December 2006 on the addition of vitamins, minerals and certain other substances to foods.
- **REGULATION (EU) No 1169/2011** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2011 on the provision of food information to consumers and amending Regulations (EC) No 1924/2006 and (EC) No 1925/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council.
- **REGULATION (EC) No 1333/2008** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on food additives.
- **COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 1129/2011** of 11 November 2011 amending Annex II to Regulation (EC) No 1333/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council to by establishing a Union list of food additives.

- **Regulation (EC) No 178/2002** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety.
- **REGULATION (EC) No 1924/2006** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 December 2006 on nutritional and health claims made on foods.
- **Commission REGULATION (EU) No 1047/2012** of 8 November 2012 amending Regulation (EC) No 1924/2006 as regards the list of nutrition claims.
- **DIRECTIVE 1999/41/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT** and of the Council of 7 June 1999 amending Council Directive 89/398/EEC on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to foodstuffs intended
- for particular nutritional uses.
- **COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) No 307/2012** of 11 April laying down detailed rules for the application of Article 8 of Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the addition of vitamins, minerals and certain other substances to foods.
- **COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) No 489/2012** of 8 June laying down detailed rules for the application of Article 16 of Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the addition of vitamins, minerals and certain other substances to foods.
- **DIRECTIVE (EU) 2020/2184** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on the quality of water intended for human consumption.
- **REGULATION (EC) 2073/2005** of 15 November 2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs.
- **Commission REGULATION (EC) 282/2008** of 27 March 2008 on recycled plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food and amending Regulation (EC) No 2023/2006.
- **Commission REGULATION (EU) 10/2011** of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles **intended** to come into contact with food.

- **COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2018/213** of 12 February 2018 on the use of bisphenol A in varnishes and coatings intended to come into contact with food and amending Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 as regards the use of that substance in plastic materials in contact with food.
- **REGULATION (EC) No. 1935/2004** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 2004 on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food and repealing Directives 80/590/EEC and 89/109/EEC.
- **COMMISSION REGULATION (EC) No 1881/2006** of 19 December 2006 setting maximum level for certain contaminants in foodstuffs.
- **Commission Regulation (EU) 2021/1317** of 9 August 2021 amending Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 as regards maximum levels for lead in certain foodstuffs.
- **Commission Regulation (EU) 2021/1323** of 10 August 2021 amending Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 as regards the maximum level of cadmium in certain foodstuffs.
- **REGULATION (EU) 2018/848** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 on organic production and labelling of organic products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007.

FERMENTED DESSERTS

- **REGULATION 852/2004 OF 29 APRIL 2004** of the European Parliament and of the Council on the hygiene of foodstuffs.
- **COMMISSION DECISION (EU) 2018/1701** of 7 November 2018 on the proposal for a citizens' initiative entitled 'Mandatory labelling of foods as non-vegetarian/vegetarian/vegan'.
- **REGULATION (EU) 2015/2283** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2015 on novel foods, amending Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Regulation (EC) No 258/97 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Commission Regulation (EC) No 1852/2001.
- **Commission IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) 2017/2470** of 20 December 2017 establishing the Union list of novel foods in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 of the European Parliament and of the Council on novel foods.
- **REGULATION (EC) No 178/2002** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and laying down procedures in matters of food safety.
- **REGULATION (EC) No 852/2004** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs.
- **COMMISSION REGULATION (EC) No 1881/2006** of 19 December 2006 setting maximum level for certain contaminants in foodstuffs.
- **Commission REGULATION (EU) 2021/1317** of 9 August 2021 amending Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 as regards maximum levels for lead in certain foodstuffs.
- **Commission REGULATION (EU) 2021/1323** of 10 August 2021 amending Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 as regards the maximum level of cadmium in certain foodstuffs.
- **Commission REGULATION (EU) 10/2011** of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food.

- **COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2018/213** of 12 February 2018 on the use of bisphenol A in varnishes and coatings intended to come into contact with food and amending Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 as regards the use of that substance in plastic materials in contact with food.
- **REGULATION (EC) No 1935/2004** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 2004 on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food and repealing Directives 80/590/EEC and 89/109/EEC.
- **REGULATION (EC) 2073/2005** of 15 November 2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs, published in OJ L 338 OF 22.12.2005.
- **DIRECTIVE (EU) 2020/2184** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2020 on the quality of water intended for human consumption.
- **REGULATION (EU) No 1169/2011** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2011 on the provision of food information to consumers and amending Regulations (EC) No 1924/2006 and (EC) No 1925/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council.
- **REGULATION (EC) No 1333/2008** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on food additives.
- **COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 1129/2011** of 11 November 2011
- amending Annex II to Regulation (EC) No 1333/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council to establish a list of Union food additives.
- **REGULATION (EC) 178/2011** on the principles and requirements of food law, establishment of EFSA and regulation of food safety.
- **REGULATION (EC) No 1924/2006** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 December 2006 on nutrition and health claims made on foods.
- **Commission REGULATION (EU) No 1047/2012** of 8 November 2012 amending Regulation (EC) No 1924/2006 as regards the list of nutrition claims
- **REGULATION (EU) No 1308/2013** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on the common organisation of the markets in agricultural products and repealing Council Regulations (EEC) No 922/72, (EEC) No 234/79, (EC) No 1037/2001 and (EC) No 1234/2007 (OJ 2013 L 347, p. 671).

- **COURT OF JUSTICE OF THE EUROPEAN UNION TO JUDGEMENT IN CASE C-422/16** purely plant products may not be placed on the market under names such as 'milk', 'cream', 'butter', 'cheese' or 'yoghourt', reserved by European Union law for products of animal origin.
 - That criterion also applies where those names are supplemented by explanatory or descriptive particulars indicating the plant origin of the product concerned. However, there is a list of exceptions.
- **COMMISSION DECISION of 20 December 2010** establishing the list of products referred to in the second subparagraph of point III (1) of Annex XII to Council Regulation (EC) No 1234/2007.
- **REGULATION (EU) 2018/848 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL** of 30 May 2018 on organic production and labelling of organic products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007.

NATURAL EXTRACTS

- **Commission IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) 2017/2470** establishing the list of novel foods compiles all novel foods authorised in the European Union to date. It includes its conditions of use, labelling requirements and specifications.
- **Commission IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) 2018/1023** of 23 July 2018 correcting Implementing Regulation (EU) 2017/2470 establishing the Union list of novel foods.
- **EEUU. FDA Section 182.20 “Essential oils, oleoresins (solvent-free), and natural extractives (including distillates)”** of Title 21, Chapter I, Subchapter B.
- **REGULATION (EC) No. 1333/2008** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on food additives.
- **Commission REGULATION (EU) No 1129/2011** of 11 November 2011 amending Annex II to Regulation (EC) No 1333/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council to establish a list of Food Additives in the Union Text with EEA relevant.
- **COMMISSION REGULATION (EC) No 1881/2006** of 19 December 2006 setting maximum level for certain contaminants in foodstuffs.
- **Commission REGULATION (EU) 2021/1317** of 9 August 2021 amending Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 as regards maximum levels for lead in certain foodstuffs.
- **Commission REGULATION (EU) 2021/1323** of 10 August 2021 amending Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 as regards the maximum level of cadmium in certain foodstuffs.

COMPOTE

- **COMMISSION REGULATION (EC) No 1425/2003** of 11 August 2003 amending Regulation (EC) No 466/2001 as regards patulin.
- **COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING REGULATION (EU) No 543/2011** of 7 June 2011 laying down detailed rules for the application of Council Regulation (EC) No 1234/2007 in the fruit and vegetables and processed fruit and vegetables sectors.
- **Regulation (EC) No 396/2005** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on maximum residue limits for pesticides in and on food and feed of plant and animal origin and amending Council Directive 91/414/EEC Text with EEA effects.
- **REGULATION (EU) No 1169/2011** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2011 on the provision of food information to consumers and amending Regulations (EC) No 1924/2006 and (EC) No 1925/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council.
- **REGULATION (EC) No 1333/2008** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on food additives.
- **COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 1129/2011** of 11 November 2011 amending Annex II to Regulation (EC) No 1333/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council to establish a list of Union food additives.
- **REGULATION (EC) 178/2002** on the principles and requirements of food law, establishment of EFSA and regulation of food safety.
- **REGULATION (EC) 2073/2005** of 15 November 2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs, published in OJ L 338 OF 22.12.2005.
- **COMMISSION REGULATION (EC) No 1881/2006** of 19 December 2006 setting maximum level for certain contaminants in foodstuffs.
- **REGULATION (EC) No 1935/2004** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 2004 on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food and repealing Directives 80/590/EEC and 89/109/EEC.
- **Regulation (EC) No 1829/2003** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 September 2003 on genetically modified food and feed.

- **Regulation (EC) No 1830/2003** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 September 2003 on the traceability and labelling of genetically modified organisms and on the traceability of food and feed produced from them, and amending Directive 2001/18/EC.
- **Directive 1999/3/EC** of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 February 1999 on the establishment of a Community list of foods and food ingredients treated with ionising radiation

2.2 New nutraceuticals formulations

A2C will develop new nutraceutical products from all the bioactive principles that remain in the value chain of agricultural and food products. Each country differs in their regulatory requirements for registration and marketing approval. It is expected to have harmonised legislation in Europe within the next few years.

Until then, the European Union classified the nutraceuticals as Food Supplements, and they are regulated as food. They are considered as Novel Food: substances other than vitamins and minerals, which are intended to be used in food supplements and do not have a history of safe use before 1997.

The current Novel Food legislation in Europe is **Regulation (EC) 2015/2283**, replacing Regulation (EC) 258/97 of the European Parliament and **Regulation (EC) 1852/2001** of the Council and Commission.

Regulation (EC) 2015/2283 establishes different categories of Novel Food. The extracts to be obtained during the project as nutraceutical can be classified in the categories: plants, and/or foods resulting from production processes and practices and state of the art technologies.

There is a Union list of authorised Novel Foods. If our products are not included in this Union list, they must comply:

- ✓ Not to be a risk for human health.
- ✓ The intended use does not induce a misuse of the product.

To apply for the inclusion in the Union list, it is necessary:

- ✓ Full description of the Novel food.
- ✓ Full description of the obtention process.
- ✓ The composition.
- ✓ Toxicity assessments.
- ✓ Method of analysis.
- ✓ Intended conditions of use and labelling requirements (i.e., for Spain they are listed in Royal Decree 130/2018).

2.3 New cosmetics formulations characteristics.

The bioactive principles obtained by extraction technology and bio-transformation of food & vegetable waste (antioxidants and building blocks) will be used in the manufacture of new cosmetic products that must comply with the following European regulations:

REGULATION (EC) No 1223/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2009 on cosmetic products.

Amended by:

- M1 – Commission Regulation (EU) No 344/2013 of 4 April 2013
- M2 – Commission Regulation (EU) No 483/2013 of 24 May 2013
- M3 – Commission Regulation (EU) No 658/2013 of 10 July 2013
- M4 – Commission Regulation (EU) No 1197/2013 of 25 November 2013
- M5 – Commission Regulation (EU) No 358/2014 of 9 April 2014
- M6 – Commission Regulation (EU) No 866/2014 of 8 August 2014
- M7 – Commission Regulation (EU) No 1003/2014 of 18 September 2014
- M8 – Commission Regulation (EU) No 1004/2014 of 18 September 2014
- M9 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2015/1190 of 20 July 2015
- M10 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2015/1298 of 28 July 2015
- M11 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/314 of 4 March 2016
- M12 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/621 of 21 April 2016
- M13 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/622 of 21 April 2016
- M14 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/1120 of 11 July 2016
- M15 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/1121 of 11 July 2016
- M16 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/1143 of 13 July 2016
- M17 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/1198 of 22 July 2016
- M18 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/237 of 10 February 2017
- M19 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/238 of 10 February 2017
- M20 – Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017
- M21 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/1224 of 6 July 2017
- M22 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/1410 of 2 August 2017

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- M23 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/1413 of 3 August 2017
- M24 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/2228 of 4 December 2017
- M25 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/885 of 20 June 2018
- M26 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/978 of 9 July 2018
- M27 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/1847 of 26 November 2018
- M28 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/680 of 30 April 2019
- M29 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/681 of 30 April 2019
- M30 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/698 of 30 April 2019
- M31 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/831 of 22 May 2019
- M32 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/1257 of 23 July 2019
- M33 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/1857 of 6 November 2019
- M34 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/1858 of 6 November 2019
- M35 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/1966 of 27 November 2019
- M36 – Regulation (EU) 2020/561 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2020
- M37 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2020/1682 of 12 November 2020
- M38 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2020/1683 of 12 November 2020
- M39 – Commission Regulation (EU) 2020/1684 of 12 November 2020
- Corrected by:
 - C1 – Corrigendum, OJ L 142, 29.5.2013, p. 10 (344/2013)
 - C2 – Corrigendum, OJ L 254, 28.8.2014, p. 39 (866/2014)
 - C3 – Corrigendum, OJ L 17, 21.1.2017, p. 52 (2016/314)
 - C4 – Corrigendum, OJ L 326, 9.12.2017, p. 55 (2017/2228)
 - C5 – Corrigendum, OJ L 183, 19.7.2018, p. 27 (2018/978)
 - C6 – Corrigendum, OJ L 324, 13.12.2019, p. 80 (2019/1966)
 - C7 – Corrigendum, OJ L 76, 12.3.2020, p. 36 (2019/1966)
 - C8 – Corrigendum, OJ L 397, 26.11.2020, p. 30 (2020/1683)

2.4 New recycled plastic specifications.

There is a great need to reuse multilayer packaging plastics used in the food sector as packaging in order to valorize them and to ensure that they are not disposable. After processing and recycling, these plastics will be in contact with food again and therefore cannot be harmful to human health, which implies compliance with tight European regulations.

<p>Regulations and requirements.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEW PACKAGING PLASTIC SPECIFICATIONS.
<p>Regulation (EC) 10/2011</p>	<p>Regulations on plastic material and articles intended to come into contact with food(i) already in contact with food or (iii) which can reasonably be expected to come into contact with food.</p> <p>Applies to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Materials and articles parts thereof, consisting exclusively of plastic. ● Plastic multi-layer materials and articles held together by adhesives. ● Materials that can be printed or covered by a coating. ● Plastic layers or plastic coatings, forming gaskets in caps and closures. ● Plastic layer in multi-material and multi-layer materials and articles <p>Key Regulation Inclusions and Requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Compositional requirements. Only authorised substances that are positive listed in Annex I of the regulation may be

	<p>intentionally used in the manufacture of plastic materials and articles.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific provisions for several categories of plastic materials Caps and closures and multi-layer plastic materials or multi material multilayers • Declaration of Compliance (DoC) A DoC is required at all stages of production and marketing (excluding the retail stage) and it needs to be supported by appropriate underlying documentation. • Testing requirements. Requirements for testing of overall and specific migration, including comprehensive guidance on selecting simulants and conditions for testing. • Risk Assessment Added Substances (NIAS) and their risk, by the manufacturer of plastic food contact materials and articles.
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Regulations and requirements.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NEW PLASTIC SPECIFICATIONS.
Amendment EU 2020/1245 of Regulation (EU) 10/2020.	<p>Based on scientific assessments by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), amendments are now proposed to Annexes I and II to Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 on plastic food contact materials. At the same time, changes are added to the migration scenarios and the text on the testing of products for repeated use is clarified, among other things. The amendment came into force on 23rd September 2020 with a transition period of two years, until 23 September 2022. For Plastic materials and articles that comply with Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 and which are first placed on the market before 23 March 2021 , they will remain on the market until the exhaustion of stocks.</p>

<p>UNE-EN 13655:2018</p>	<p>Plastic, Thermoplastic mulch films recoverable after use, for use in agriculture and horticulture.</p> <p>This document specifies the requirements related to dimensional, mechanical, optical and thermal characteristics of thermoplastic films for mulching.</p> <p>These mulches are intended to be removed after use and not incorporated in the soil.</p> <p>These mulch films are not intended to be used for soil disinfection by fumigation.</p>
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2.5 New bioplastics compounds specifications.

The formulation of biodegradable plastics and their biodegradability will be studied to determine their ability to biodegrade in different natural and industrial environments, as well as the extent to which they can be used repeatedly without impairing their properties.

<p>Regulations and requirements.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIODEGRADABILITY OF PLASTIC MATERIALS IN COMPOST.
<p>Standard UNE-EN ISO 14855:2:2019</p>	<p>Specifies a method for the determination of the ultimate aerobic biodegradability of plastics, based on organic compounds, under controlled composting conditions by measurement of the amount of carbon dioxide evolved and the degree of disintegration of the plastic at the end of the test.</p>

- The test material is exposed to an inoculum which is derived from compost.
- The composting takes place in an environment wherein temperature, aeration and humidity are closely monitored and controlled.

The test method is designed to yield the percentage conversion of the carbon in the test material to evolved carbon dioxide as well as the rate of conversion.

The standard establishes a sample as biodegradable when in a maximum time of 180 days (6 month) reaches 90% of biodegradation.

2.6 New agricultural film characteristics.

Plastics from agriculture can be reused again if an adequate method of decontamination is achieved, which will be one of the objectives to be able to be reused as plastic in contact with food. Biodegradable films must be biodegradable in soil while maintaining their mechanical characteristics during their lifetime. New agricultural films have to meet the following standard:

Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BIODEGRADABLE MULCH FILMS FOR USE IN AGRICULTURE AND HORTICULTURE
UNE-EN 17033:2018	<p>This standard specifies the requirements for biodegradable films, manufactured from thermoplastic materials, to be used for mulch applications in agriculture and horticulture.</p> <p>Applicable to films intended to biodegrade in soil without creating any adverse impact on the environment. It also specifies the test methods to assess these requirements as</p>

	<p>well as requirements for the packaging, identification and marking of films.</p> <p>For information, it defines a classification of biodegradable mulch films according to their service life on soil and gives a good practice guide for the use of the films.</p>
<p>EN 13655-2018</p>	<p>This document specifies the requirements related to dimensional, mechanical, optical and thermal characteristics of thermoplastic films for mulching applications in agriculture and horticulture.</p> <p>These mulch films are intended to be removed after use and not incorporated in the soil. These mulch films are not intended to be used for soil disinfection by fumigation.</p> <p>It specifies a classification for durability of mulching films and the test methods referred to in this document.</p> <p>This document is applicable to thermoplastic mulch films, used for agriculture and horticulture in Europe, based on polyethylene and/or ethylene copolymers, of the following types: - transparent films; - black films; - reflective films (e.g. white films, black/white films and black/silver films); - films of other colour(s) for weed control (e.g. green, brown). This document also defines installation, use and removal conditions of mulch films.</p>
<p>EN 17098-1:2018</p>	<p>Specifies the requirements relating to the dimensional, mechanical and physical-chemical characteristics of</p>

	<p>thermoplastic barrier films designed for agricultural and horticultural soil disinfection by means of fumigation.</p> <p>This document also specifies the test methods for verifying these requirements, except the method for determining film permeability using a static technique, which is specified in EN 17098-2. This document defines guidance for installation, use and disposal of barrier films.</p> <p>This document is applicable to films used during soil disinfection by fumigation (class1) and to films used during soil disinfection subsequently kept in situ as mulch films (class2) .</p>				
<p>Regulations and requirements.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● BIODEGRADABILITY OF PLASTIC MATERIALS IN COMPOST. 				
<p>Standard UNE-EN 17033</p>	<p>Regulates the requirements for biodegradable plastic mulch films and the test procedures for the following properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Chemical Composition (in particular for regulated metals and hazardous substances) ● Biodegradability in soil ● Ecotoxicity (effect on the soil environment) ● Mechanical and optical properties <p>It does not apply to mulch from the fields that are being removed from the field after use.</p> <table border="0" data-bbox="432 1765 1337 1921"> <tr> <td>Criterion</td> <td>Test Method</td> </tr> <tr> <td>I Constituents</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	Criterion	Test Method	I Constituents	
Criterion	Test Method				
I Constituents					

- Concentrations limits for heavy metals
- No hazardous substances of “very high concern” (<0.1%)

EN 17294-2

- Loss of ignition at 550°C ($\geq 60^\circ$)

II Biodegradation

- $\geq 90\%$ conversion of mulch’s carbon into CO₂ within two years under soil conditions.

ISO 17556

III Ecotoxicity

- No acute ecotoxicity to plants ($\geq 90\%$ of germination rate and plant growth achieved compared to mulch free soil)

ISO 11268-1

- No acute ecotoxicity to invertebrates (<10% difference in mortality rate and biomass amount compared to mulch free soil).

- No acute toxicity to microorganisms (nitrification inhibition of bacteria should be $\geq 80\%$ of that achieved for Biodegradable mulch- free soil)

ISO-1568

IV Dimensional, mechanical, and optical properties.

- Tensile stress at break ≥ 18 MPa (MD); ≥ 16 MPa (TD)
- Light transmission of $\leq 3\%$ (only for black and opaque films)

V Labelling and surface area

- Proper labelling; preparation of a test report by manufacturer.
- Surface area

2.7 New food packaging characteristics

Due to the great need to reduce the use of conventional plastics, new compositions of biodegradable plastics with properties similar to those currently used for packaging will be formulated.

New food packaging has to meet the following characteristics:

Applications:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FLEXIBLE BIODEGRADABLE PACKAGING FOR FROZEN FOOD
Process constraints	<p>Extrusion up to 3 layers. Printing Flexographic.</p>
Mechanical properties	<p>Thickness: (ISO 4593:2010): 55µm. Tear resistance:(Elmendorf method) (ISO 6383-2:1983): 2500 mN (MD); 1500 mN (TD). Tensile Resistance (UNE-EN ISO 527-3 UNE 53942) Resistance at break: 20 N (MD); 18N(TD). Elongation at break: 350%(MD); 420%(TD). Dart impact (ISO 7665-1):>200g. Density: 1.30-1.35 g/cm³.</p>
OTR/WVT Barrier properties	<p>No special barrier requirements needed for frozen foodstuffs.</p>
Thermal properties	<p>Extrusion temperature 130-165°C.</p>

Optical properties	Opacity=65% (for white materials)
Biodegradable properties	Meet the 13432 standard

Standard UNE.EN 13432: setting out compostable characteristics	<p>Requirements for packaging recoverable through composting and biodegradation. Test scheme and evaluation criteria for the final acceptance of packaging.</p> <p>Compostable packaging must have the following main characteristic:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Biodegradability. <p>Test is a measure of the extent to which the product is converted to water, carbon dioxide and/or biomass by means of microbial action.</p> <p>Shall be demonstrated through laboratory testing and carried out to the correct methodology i.e.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) ISO: 14855- Biodegradability under controlled aerobic composting conditions. 2) ISO: 14851. Aerobic degradability in water (oxygen demand) 3) ISO 14852. Aerobic degradability in water (evolved carbon dioxide) <p>Test is carried for a maximum of 6 months, by which time the amount of carbon dioxide released must be at least 90% as much carbon dioxide given off by a reference/ control sample.</p> ● Disintegration <p>Test designed to quantify the “physical falling apart into small fragments of packaging and packaging materials”</p> <p>Test is carried out on the end product specification as feasible.</p> <p>A sample of the test material is added to an organic waste</p>
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fraction and is then sustained under relevant pilot-scale testing conditions at 58°C for 12 weeks.

The standard requires that at the end of the period at least 90% of material must pass through a 2mm sieve.

- **Ecotoxicity**

The residue from disintegration testing is utilised for ecotoxicity analysis the aim of which is to highlight any potential negative effect on the compost material.

Test method:

Comparison of samples, one with and one without product material, which have gone through the disintegration tests are used to determine any negative toxicological effects e.g. pH, volatile solids, salinity, magnesium, N; P, K and ammonium nitrogen. The use of two higher plant tests which conform to the requirements of the OECD 208 “Terrestrial Plants Growth

Test method

The number of grown plants and the plant biomass within the sample and control sample are compared. Percentage is provided against the blank compost. The percent should be no less than 90% of the blank sample.

- **Chemical Analysis**

Heavy metal concentrations are used to indicate any potential negative effects of the end compost quality. Especially important to composters going down a quality route.

Test method

Disclosure of all chemical element concentrations must be given to the certifying body as a way of disclosing the presence of hazardous substances. Analysis of heavy metals is normally undertaken by the manufacturer of each constituent.

Threshold concentrations are shown in the EN 13432 standard.

Applications:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FLEXIBLE RECYCLABLE PACKAGING FOR SNACKS.
Process constraints	<p>Extrusion up to 5 layers. Printing Flexographic. Lamination, solventless or with solvent.</p>
Mechanical properties	<p>Thickness: (ISO 4593:2010): 82µm. Tear resistance:(Elmendorf method) (ISO 6383-2:1983): 495 mN (MD); 542 mN (TD). Tensile resistance (UNE-EN ISO 527-3) Resistance at break:(UNE 53942),47,8 N (MD); 50,7 N(TD). Elongation at break: 350%(MD); 420%(TD). Dart impact (ISO 7665-1).</p>
OTR/WVTR Barrier properties	<p>Barrier to oxygen:125 cc/m² 24 hours (23°C y 0%HR) Barrier to water vapour transmission:<1 G/M² 24 hours (38°C y 90% HR)</p>
Optical properties	<p>HAZE: PET 4%, complex:<6%</p>

Regulations and requirements.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PACKAGING MATERIALS FOR FRESH FRUITS AND VEGETABLES.
Regulation (EC) 1935/2004 and Regulation 10/2011.	<p>Regulations on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food.</p>
UNE-EN 13432:2001	<p>Requirements for packaging recoverable through composting and biodegradation. Test scheme and evaluation criteria for the final acceptance of packaging.</p>

UNE-EN 17033:2018	Biodegradable mulch films for use in agriculture and horticulture. Requirements and test methods.
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2.8 New Data Integration System

The Data Integration System is an online technological platform that solves industry challenges by collecting data throughout the full life cycle. It facilitates proper waste management at the level of agricultural producers and agri-food companies to comply with regulatory requirements, improves the efficiency of the logistics chain for the collection of these wastes, predicts the characteristics of agri-food waste streams, and explores all available alternatives to select the best recovery route for each waste. It helps all agents in the supply chain to comply with the European Standard UNE 15343:2008 on traceability of plastic recycling and conformity assessment and recycled content.

In the A2C project scope, it encounters public administrations, giving an easier access to data on agri-food waste management for more efficient management of the processes it supervises. There is a cost reduction in auditing and control processes, as well as a more precise knowledge of the content of recycled materials and traceability for control authorities. Moreover, for technical partners it provides real-time information on waste management and acceptance. Information that allows them to optimise logistics and provide services more efficiently.

The Data Integration System has to meet the following specifications and characteristics:

- **Communication**

- With A2C users
 - By means of a WEB address, the contents will be accessed.
 - Depending on the type of user, they will access the content that they can see and is of interest to them.
- With "ECO" technology partners
 - Through collaborative WEB platforms.
 - Technological tools for communication between development applications.

- **Features**

- With A2C users

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

A2C – Deliverable D1.1V2.0

- Users will be able to consult all the data incorporated into the DIS
- With A2C producers
 - Management tools for:
 - Data entry
 - Characterization of raw materials and transformed products.
 - Internal transformation process.
 - The process between partners for transformation.
 - Associated information.
 - Normative
 - Binding.
- With ECO providers
 - Technological tools for
 - Communication between machines.
 - Security in access and communication between machines.
 - Containers and data contents.
 - Information structure for:
 - Characterization data.
 - Process data.
 - Data for traceability.
 - Data for calculations:
 - Statistics.
 - Projections
 - Cycle times.
 - Forecasts.
- **Contents**
 - A2C users
 - Information about A2C Transformer Partners
 - Raw Materials
 - Products
 - Traceability
 - Non-producer partner information
 - Corporate information.

A2C – Deliverable D1.1V2.0

- Services information.
- Information from Technological Partners.
 - Corporate information.
 - Information about products and services.
- DIS information
 - Route of raw materials and products in the circular economy.
 - Socio-economic effects of the circular economy.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The Characteristics and specifications of the product that are going to be developed have been defined:

- The regulations that new food formulations must comply with have been identified.
- The characteristics of nutraceutical products have been defined.
- The characteristics of cosmetic formulations have also been defined.

These specifications will be used for the developments of these specific products, WP4 task 4.1 “Formulations of the extracts at small scale “ and WP6 task 6.2 “A2C demonstrators, and for the assessment of the extracted bioactives, WP2 task 2.4 “Evaluation of the extracts “, WP4 task 4.2.2 “Validation of the extracts obtained at pilot scale-up” and WP5 Task 5.1.1 “Upcycling of TPA, EG and alkanes to building blocks by biotechnological routes”. Also they will be taking into account in WP1 task 1.2.2 “New food, nutraceuticals & cosmetics formulations assessment & compliance to standards”

- The specifications to be met by the recycled plastic have been identified.
- The standards that bioplastic composites must meet have been identified.
- The characteristics of the new agricultural films have been established taking into account the EN 17033 standard and barrier requirements.
- The characteristics of the new food packaging have been established characteristics have been established taking into account the EN 13432 standard.

The specifications for the evaluation of the different plastic products will be used in WP3 task 3.5.3 “Additivation and development of processable recycled plastic compounds” , WP5 task 5.2 “High barrier recycled and recyclable compounds for food packaging and agricultural films” task 5.3 “Biodegradable compounds for food packaging and agricultural films” and task 5.4 “Compounds transformation into food packaging and agricultural films at small scale” and WP6 task 6.2 “demonstrators”. They will also be used in WP1 Task 1.2.1 “Plastics food contact assessment & compliance to agriculture standards”

A2C – Deliverable D1.1V2.0

- The characteristics of the Data Integration System have been defined and will be used in WP1 task 1.5 “A2C Data Integration System (DIS)” and WP6 task 6.2 “Demonstrator”.

4 ANNEXES

ANNEX I - FT New food, nutraceutical and cosmetics formulations.

	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION
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LEMON JUICE WITH FIBRE

Description: Our Single Strength Lemon Juice (N.F.C.) is a natural product obtained by squeezing naturally matured, sound lemons and enriched with natural lemon fibre. The product is pasteurized, chilled and frozen to assure its preservation. It contains no additives.

Raw material botanical name: Citrus limon (L.) Burm.f.

Application: Any foodstuff application. Fit for direct consumption. For industrial use only.

Specifications:

SENSORIC	Colour	Pale yellow	
	Odour/Taste	Characteristic of fresh lemon	
	Appearance	Fluid liquid, slightly viscous, stable, without strange particles, peel or seeds	
		Min	Max
PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL	°Brix (uncorrected 20°C)	7	11
	°Brix (corrected 20°C)	7.8	12.4
	Acidity (% acid citric anhydrous)	4	7
	Pulp content (%v/v)	0.5	7
	Recoverable oil (%)		0.06
	pH	2.0	3.0
	Content in fibre (%)	1.5	5
MICROBIOLOGICAL	Mesophilic aerobes (Orange serum agar)		1000 c.f.u./ml
	Yeast-Mould (Saboraud cloranfenicol glucose agar)		500 c.f.u./ml

Packaging: Standard 230 litres open top steel drums with double polyliners (net weight 200 kg) and bulk by isothermal tankers. The product can also be supplied in plastic bottles (1 litre), plastic pails (20 litres), jerrycans (25 litres) or IBC containers (1000 litres) upon request. All the packaging is food grade and meets the Regulation EU No 10/2011 and subsequent amendments.

Labelling: Each package is clearly labelled with a product description, batch reference, production date, shelf-life and net weight.

Transport conditions:

- Isothermal tankers with temperatures between 0°C and 4°C.
- Other packagings in frozen transport below -18°C.

Usage conditions:

- Defrosting between 8-10 days with temperatures between 0°C and 5°C.
- There is a risk of fermentation if defrosting is done at higher temperatures.

Storage & shelf life:

- Best before 2 years (storage at -18°C).
- Best before 7 days (storage from 0 to 5°C).

REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS THAT THE PRODUCT MEETS

1. Good manufacturing practices and food safety

- COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2001/112/EC of 20 December 2001 relating to fruit juices and certain similar products intended for human consumption and amendments.
- REGULATION (EC) No 852/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs

2. Pesticides and contaminants

- Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 of 19 December 2006 setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs and amendments.
- Regulation (EC) No. 396/2005 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin and amending Council Directive 91/414/EEC and amendments.

3. Allergens / GMO / Ionising radiations

- Total absence of allergen substances according to REGULATION (EC) No 1169/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2011 on the provision of food information to consumers and amendments.
- In accordance with Regulations 1829/2003 (on labelling and traceability) and 1830/2003 (on genetically modified food) and their amending legislation of the European Parliament, this product does not contain any GMOs (including additives and flavourings), was not produced from any GMOs, was not manufactured using GMOs or products from GMOs and is not subject to the labelling obligation.
- In compliance with the Directive 1999/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 February 1999 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States concerning foods and food ingredients treated with ionising radiation, and the Directive 1999/3/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 February 1999 on the establishment of a Community list of foods and food ingredients treated with ionising radiation, this product is not treated with ionising radiation and does not contain any ingredient treated with ionising radiation.

	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION
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LEMON JUICE WITH FLAVONOIDS

Description: Our Single Strength Lemon Juice (N.F.C.) is a natural product obtained by squeezing naturally matured, sound lemons and enriched with natural lemon flavonoids. The product is pasteurized, chilled and frozen to assure its preservation. It contains no additives.

Raw material botanical name: Citrus limon (L.) Burm.f.

Application: Any foodstuff application. Fit for direct consumption. For industrial use only.

Specifications:

SENSORIC	Colour	Pale yellow	
	Odour/Taste	Characteristic of fresh lemon	
	Appearance	Fluid liquid, slightly viscous, stable, without strange particles, peel or seeds	
		Min	Max
PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL	°Brix (uncorrected 20°C)	7	11
	°Brix (corrected 20°C)	7.8	12.4
	Acidity (% acid citric anhydrous)	4	7
	Pulp content (%v/v)	0.5	7
	Recoverable oil (%)		0.06
	pH	2.0	3.0
	Content in flavonoids (mg/100ml)	30	
MICROBIOLOGICAL	Mesophilic aerobes (Orange serum agar)		1000 c.f.u./ml
	Yeast-Mould (Saboraud cloranfenicol glucose agar)		500 c.f.u./ml

Packaging: Standard 230 litres open top steel drums with double polyliners (net weight 200 kg) and bulk by isothermal tankers. The product can also be supplied in plastic bottles (1 litre), plastic pails (20 litres), jerrycans (25 litres) or IBC containers (1000 litres) upon request. All the packaging is food grade and meets the Regulation EU No 10/2011 and subsequent amendments.

Labelling: Each package is clearly labelled with a product description, batch reference, production date, shelf-life and net weight.

Transport conditions:

- Isothermal tankers with temperatures between 0°C and 4°C.
- Other packagings in frozen transport below -18°C.

Usage conditions:

- Defrosting between 8-10 days with temperatures between 0°C and 5°C.
- There is a risk of fermentation if defrosting is done at higher temperatures.

Storage & shelf life:

- Best before 2 years (storage at -18°C).
- Best before 7 days (storage from 0 to 5°C).

REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS THAT THE PRODUCT MEETS

1. Good manufacturing practices and food safety

- COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2001/112/EC of 20 December 2001 relating to fruit juices and certain similar products intended for human consumption and amendments.
- REGULATION (EC) No 852/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs

2. Pesticides and contaminants

- Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 of 19 December 2006 setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs and amendments.
- Regulation (EC) No. 396/2005 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin and amending Council Directive 91/414/EEC and amendments.

3. Allergens / GMO / Ionising radiations

- Total absence of allergen substances according to REGULATION (EC) No 1169/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2011 on the provision of food information to consumers and amendments.
- In accordance with Regulations 1829/2003 (on labelling and traceability) and 1830/2003 (on genetically modified food) and their amending legislation of the European Parliament, this product does not contain any GMOs (including additives and flavourings), was not produced from any GMOs, was not manufactured using GMOs or products from GMOs and is not subject to the labelling obligation.
- In compliance with the Directive 1999/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 February 1999 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States concerning foods and food ingredients treated with ionising radiation, and the Directive 1999/3/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 February 1999 on the establishment of a Community list of foods and food ingredients treated with ionising radiation, this product is not treated with ionising radiation and does not contain any ingredient treated with ionising radiation.

	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION
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LEMON FIBRE EXTRACT

Description: The Lemon Fibre extract is a natural product obtained by separating the pulp and the peel from the freshly squeezed juice of naturally, matured, sound lemons. It contains no additives.

Raw material botanical name: Citrus limon (L.) Burm.f.

Application: Any foodstuff application. Not fit for direct consumption. For industrial use only.

Specifications:

SENSORIC	Colour	White to cream	
	Odour/Taste	Odourless/Tasteless	
	Appearance	Powder	
		Min	Max
PHYSICAL- CHEMICAL	Humidity (%)		12
	Particle size (mm)		0.4
	Water retention (g/g)	10	
	Oil retention (g/g)	2	
	Sweeling (ml/g)	10	
	Total dietary fibre (% w/w)	70	
MICROBIOLOGICAL	Mesophilic aerobes (Orange serum agar)		20000 c.f.u./ml
	Yeast-Mould (Saboraud cloranfenicol glucose agar)		20000 c.f.u./ml

Transport conditions:

- In ambient temperature transport.

Storage & shelf life:

- Best before 2 years (storage at ambient temperature in a cool place).

REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS THAT THE PRODUCT MEETS

1. Good manufacturing practices and food safety

- COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2001/112/EC of 20 December 2001 relating to fruit juices and certain similar products intended for human consumption and amendments.

- REGULATION (EC) No 852/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs

2. Pesticides and contaminants

- Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 of 19 December 2006 setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs and amendments.

- Regulation (EC) No. 396/2005 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin and amending Council Directive 91/414/EEC and amendments.

	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION
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3. Allergens / GMO / Ionising radiations

- Total absence of allergen substances according to REGULATION (EC) No 1169/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2011 on the provision of food information to consumers and amendments.
- In accordance with Regulations 1829/2003 (on labelling and traceability) and 1830/2003 (on genetically modified food) and their amending legislation of the European Parliament, this product does not contain any GMOs (including additives and flavourings), was not produced from any GMOs, was not manufactured using GMOs or products from GMOs and is not subject to the labelling obligation.
- In compliance with the Directive 1999/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 February 1999 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States concerning foods and food ingredients treated with ionising radiation, and the Directive 1999/3/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 February 1999 on the establishment of a Community list of foods and food ingredients treated with ionising radiation, this product is not treated with ionising radiation and does not contain any ingredient treated with ionising radiation.

	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION
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Product	Fruit+Milk Drink with fibre - Tropical - semi			
Legal denomination	Mixed fruit juice and milk soft drink.			
	<i>Partially from concentrate. Fruit content: 15% minimum. With sugar and sweeteners.</i>			
	<i>Source of fiber and vitamin A, C and E.</i>			
Ingredients:	Water, fruits juice: pineapple (7%), mango (3%), banana (3%), passion fruit (1%) and guava (1%) partially from concentrate, skimmed milk (10%), sugar, glucose-fructose syrup, acid regulator: citric acid (E330), sweeteners (E955, E950), fibre, stabiliser: pectin (E440), vitamins A, C y E y flavours.			
		<i>Target</i>	<i>Range</i>	
Physical-Chemical parameters	Refractometric °Brix	8	≥ 8,2	
	Acidity (% ACA)	0,35	± 0,1	
	pH	3	± 0,5	
	Density (g/ml)	1,033		
Nutritional facts Typical values per 100g of product	Energy	165	kJ	
	Fats	0,1	g	
	· of which saturates	0	g	
	Carbohydrate	7,7	g	
	· of which sugars	7,1	g	
	Fibre	3	g	
	Proteins	0,4	g	
	Salt	0,01	g	
	<i>Vitamin A</i>	<i>120</i>	<i>µg</i>	<i>(15% RDA)</i>
	<i>Vitamin C</i>	<i>40</i>	<i>mg</i>	<i>(50% RDA)</i>
<i>Vitamin E</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>mg</i>	<i>(15% RDA)</i>	
Microbiological characteristics	Product commercially sterile: absence of physical, chemical, or sensory alteration after incubation. Pasteurised product. Absence of microorganisms and derived substances in amounts which may represent a hazard to health.			
Best Before dating and storage	Best before 24 months from production date. Keep in a cool and dry place (best 10-25°C and humidity <80%) and protected from direct light. Once opened keep closed and refrigerated and consume within 4 days.			

Conformity / Authenticity / Labelling notices

The ingredients are in accordance with the AIN standards and the Spanish and European legislation, specifically the EU Directive 2012/12 and RD 781/2013.

· **Allergens: Contains MILK.** Absence of cereals with gluten, crustaceans, eggs, fish, peanuts, soy, nuts, celery, mustard, sesame, lupins, molluscs and their derivatives, and sulfur dioxide and sulphites in concentrations >10 ppm (EU Regulation 1169/2011).

· **"GMO-free"** product: No genetically modified substances have been used either as product ingredients or in the manufacturing process (Regulations CE 1829/2003 and CE 1830/2003).

· **"NOT irradiated"** product: No irradiation techniques have been used in the process or final product (Directives 1999/2/CE and 1999/3/CE).

· The product complies with the rest of the applicable legislation, and specifically with regard to levels of pesticides, heavy metals, mycotoxins and other contaminants and the suitability of packaging materials (EU Regulations 396/2005, EC 1881/2006 and EC 1935/2004).

Developed by Quality Manager

Approved by Technical Manager

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION
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Product	Multifruit nectar - with sweeteners and citrus extract				
Legal denomination	Multifruit nectar - with sweeteners - partially from concentrate - minimum fruit content 50%				
Ingredients:	Water, peach puree (10%), apricot puree (10%), apple juice from concentrate (8%), pear puree (8%), banana puree concentrate (4%), grape juice from concentrate (4%), orange juice from concentrate (3%) and mandarin juice from concentrate (3%), acid: citric acid, antioxidant: ascorbic acid, sweeteners: E955 and E950. Citrus extract.				
Physical-chemical parameters		<i>Target</i>	<i>Range</i>		
	Refractometric °Brix	5,2	≥ 5		
	Acidity (% ACA)	0,36	≥ 0,36		
	pH	3,50	± 0,50		
	Density (g/ml)	1,021	≥ 1,019		
Nutritional facts Typical values per 100 ml of product	Energy	126	kJ	30	kcal
	Fat	0,1	g		
	· of which saturates	0	g		
	Carbohydrate	6,4	g		
	· of which sugars	5,2	g		
	Protein	0,2	g		
	Salt	0	g		
Microbiology	Product commercially sterile: absence of physical, chemical or sensory alteration after incubation. Pasteurised product. Absence of microorganisms and derived substances in amounts which may represent a hazard to health.				
Organoleptic	Colour - Typical Taste and Odour - Typical Texture - Typical				
Shelf life and storage	BB from production date: 18 months in glass jar / 24 months in brick pack Keep in a cool and dry place and protected from direct light. Once opened keep closed and refrigerated and consume within 4 days.				
Primary packaging	Glass jar or brick pack Various formats.				

Conformity / Authenticity / Labelling notices

- Ingredients meet AEN standards and European and Spanish legislation, specifically Directive EU 2012/12 and RD 781/2013
- Product is "allergen-free": Absence of cereals containing gluten, crustaceans, eggs, fish, peanuts, soy, milk, nuts, celery, mustard, sesame, lupine, molluscs and its derivatives. Absence of sulphur dioxide and residual sulphites > 10 ppm (EU Regulation 1169/2011 and updating). No ingredients of animal origin.
- Product "GMO-free": No GMO elements been used as ingredients not in the production process (Regulations EU 1829/2003 and EU 1830/2003 and updating).
- Product "Irradiation-free": No irradiation techniques have been used in the process or final product (Directives 1999/2/UE and 1999/3/UE and updating)
- Product complies with every applicable regulation, and specifically those regarding presence of pesticides, heavy metals, mycotoxins and other contaminants. Also meets regulations on suitability of packaging materials (Regulations EU 396/2005, EU 1881/2006 and EU 1935/2004 and updating)

Created by Quality Manager

Approved by Technical Manager

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION
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Product Fruits Puree with fibre - Apple-Plum

Legal denomination Apple-Plum puree

Ingredients: apple puree (60%) and plum puree (40%).

	<i>Target</i>	<i>Range</i>	
Physical-chemical parameters	Refractometric °Brix	13,6	≥ 12
	Acidity (% ACA)	0,50	≤ 0,60
	pH	3,5	3,5 ± 0,5
	Density (g/ml)	1,055	
Nutritional facts Typical values per 100 ml of product	Energy	262 kJ	62 kcal
	Fat	0,2 g	
	· of which saturates	0 g	
	Carbohydrate	14,0 g	
	· of which sugars	12,0 g	
	Dietary fibre	1,4 g	
	Protein	0,3 g	
	Salt	<0,1 g	

Microbiology Product commercially sterile: absence of physical, chemical or sensory alteration after incubation. Pasteurised product. Absence of microorganisms and derived substances in amounts which may represent a hazard to health.

Shelf life and storage BB from production date: 12 months
Keep in a cool and dry place and protected from direct light. Single-use product, total consumption is recommended.

Primary packaging Tub-type container, previously thermoformed. Translucent composite material with a total thickness of 950 microns. 60 micron polyethylene layer in contact with food. 28 µm three-layer polyethylene cap. Fit for food use.

Conformity / Authenticity / Labelling notices

- Ingredients meet AIJN standards and European and Spanish legislation.
- Product is "**allergen-free**": Absence of cereals containing gluten, crustaceans, eggs, fish, peanuts, soy, milk, nuts, celery, mustard, sesame, lupine, molluscs and its derivatives. Absence of sulphur dioxide and residual sulphites > 10 ppm (EU Regulation 1169/2011). No ingredients of animal origin.
- Product "**GMO-free**": No GMO elements been used as ingredients not in the production process (Regulations EU 1829/2003 and EU 1830/2003).
- Product "**Irradiation-free**": No irradiation techniques have been used in the process or final product (Directives 1999/2/UE and 1999/3/UE)
- Product complies with every applicable regulation, and specifically those regarding presence of pesticides, heavy metals, mycotoxins and other contaminants. Also meets regulations on suitability of packaging materials (Regulations EU 396/2005, EU 1881/2006 and EU 1935/2004)

Created by Quality Manager

Approved by Technical Manager

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

	Laboratorios Almond SL	
	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION	

Denomination: NaturGreen Almond Cacao Bio (2x125 g)	
Origin: Agricultura UE/No-UE	Quality: Ecological

Description

Organic vegetable dessert, almond and chocolate flavour

Ingredients

Water, cane sugar*, almonds *(8%), partially defatted cocoa * (1,9%), corn starch*, tapioca starch*, cocoa paste * (0,9%), thickener: carob seed gum*, natural sweet almond flavouring with other natural flavourings*. Fibre
 * Ingredients from organic farming.
 "This product is manufactured in a plant where nuts, celery, soya and sesame are handled".

Nutritional values

Nutritional values	Per 100g of product	NRV
Energy value	533 kJ	0,00%
Energy value	127 kcal	0,00%
Fats	5,1 g	0,00%
of which saturated	0,8 g	0,00%
Carbohydrates	17,30 g	0,00%
Sugars	12,50 g	0,00%
Proteins	2,20 g	0,00%
Salt	0,30 g	0,00%
Dietary fibre	3,90 g	0,00%

Authorized Sanitary Registration

26.06660/MU

Authorized Sanitary Registration

Rich in fibre

Storage Conditions

Store at room temperature, in a cool and dry place.

Vida Útil

450 days

How to Use:

It can be consumed directly or used as ingredients in your pastry recipes.

Distribution Method

Sterilized product does not need refrigeration.

Textos en el envase

GLUTEN-FREE/LACTOSE-FREE

Quality parameters

Total mesophilic microorganisms -----	<1000 CFU/g
Moulds and yeasts -----	<1000 CFU/g
E.coli -----	<10 ufc/g
Coliforms -----	<10 CFU/g
Salmonella -----	absence in 25 gr
Listeria -----	absence in 25 gr
pH -----	5,2-6,5
° Brix -----	15,5-21,5

	Laboratorios Almond SL
	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION

Description of adequate consumption

This product can be consumed by any population group except those with allergies or intolerances listed in the allergen table.

List of Allergens

Allergen	Presence	Absence	Manufacturing Line
Cereals containing gluten, namely: wheat, rye, barley, oats, spelt, kamut or their hybrid varieties and products thereof.		Yes	Yes
Crustaceans and crustacean-based products.		Yes	
Eggs and egg-based products.		Yes	
Fish and fish-based products.		Yes	
Peanuts and peanut-based products.		Yes	
Soybeans and soy-based products.			Yes
Milk protein.		Yes	
Lactose		Yes	
Nuts, i.e.: almonds (<i>Amygdalus communis</i> L.), hazelnuts (<i>Corylus avellana</i>), walnuts (<i>Juglans regia</i>), cashew nuts (<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>), pecans [<i>Carya illinoensis</i> (Wangenh.) K. Koch], Brazil nuts (<i>Bertholletia excelsa</i>), pistachio nuts (<i>Pistacia vera</i>), macadamia nuts or Australian walnuts (<i>Macadamia ternifolia</i>) and products thereof, with the exception of nuts used to make alcoholic distillates, including ethyl alcohol of agricultural origin.	Yes		
Celery and derived products.			Yes
Mustard and derived products.		Yes	
Sesame grains and sesame grain products.			Yes
Sulphur dioxide and sulphites at concentrations greater than 10 mg/kg or 10 mg/litre in terms of total SO ₂ , for products ready for consumption or reconstituted according to the manufacturer's instructions.		Yes	
Lupins and lupin-based products.		Yes	
Molluscs and mollusc-based products.		Yes	

Presence: The allergen is present in the product as it is part of its list of ingredients.

Absence: The quality control protocol guarantees the absence of the allergen in the product.

Manufacturing line: The allergen is handled on the production line.

	Laboratorios Almond SL	
	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION	

Denomination: NaturGreen Almond Bio (2x125 g)

Origin: Agricultura UE/No-UE **Quality:** Ecological

Description

Organic vegetable dessert almond flavor

Ingredients

Water, cane sugar*, almonds* (9%), corn maltodextrin*, corn starch*, tapioca starch*, thickener: carob seed gum*, natural almond aroma*. Fibre.
 *Ingredients from organic farming
 "This product is manufactured in a plant where nuts, soybeans, celery and sesame are handled."

Nutritional values

Nutritional value	Per 100g of product	NRV
Energy value	500 kJ	0,00%
Energy value	119 kcal	0,00%
Fats	5,7 g	0,00%
of which saturated	0,4 g	0,00%
Carbohydrates	15,20 g	0,00%
Sugars	10,70 g	0,00%
Proteins	1,30 g	0,00%
Salt	0,10 g	0,00%
Dietary fibre	3,60g	0,00%

Authorized Sanitary Registration

26.06660/MU

Nutritional and Health Claims

Low salt content
 Low saturated fat content
 Rich in fibre

Storage Conditions

Store at room temperature, in a cool and dry place.
 Once opened keep in refrigeration and consume in 2-3 days.

Shelf life

450 days

How to Use:

It can be consumed directly or used as ingredients in your pastry recipes.

Distribution Method

Sterilized product does not need refrigeration.

Texts on the packaging

100% VEGETABLE/GLUTEN-FREE/LACTOSE-FREE/DAIRY PROTEIN-FREE

	Laboratorios Almond SL
	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION

Quality parameters

Total mesophilic microorganisms ----- <1000 CFU/g

Description of adequate consumption

This product can be consumed by any population group except those with allergies or intolerances listed in the allergen table.

List of Allergens

Allergen	Presence	Absence	Manufacturing Line
Cereals containing gluten, namely: wheat, rye, barley, oats, spelt, kamut or their hybrid varieties and products thereof.		Yes	Yes
Crustaceans and crustacean-based products.		Yes	
Eggs and egg-based products.		Yes	
Fish and fish-based products.		Yes	
Peanuts and peanut-based products.		Yes	
Soybeans and soy-based products.			Yes
Milk protein.		Yes	
Lactose		Yes	
Nuts, i.e.: almonds (<i>Amygdalus communis</i> L.), hazelnuts (<i>Corylus avellana</i>), walnuts (<i>Juglans regia</i>), cashew nuts (<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>), pecans [<i>Carya illinoensis</i> (Wangenh.) K. Koch], Brazil nuts (<i>Bertholletia excelsa</i>), pistachio nuts (<i>Pistacia vera</i>), macadamia nuts or Australian walnuts (<i>Macadamia ternifolia</i>) and products thereof, with the exception of nuts used to make alcoholic distillates, including ethyl alcohol of agricultural origin.	Yes		
Celery and derived products.			Yes
Mustard and derived products.		Yes	
Sesame grains and sesame grain products.			Yes
Sulphur dioxide and sulphites at concentrations greater than 10 mg/kg or 10 mg/litre in terms of total SO ₂ , for products ready for consumption or reconstituted according to the manufacturer's instructions.		Yes	
Lupins and lupin-based products.		Yes	
Molluscs and mollusc-based products.		Yes	

Presence: The allergen is present in the product as it is part of its list of ingredients.

Absence: The quality control protocol guarantees the absence of the allergen in the product.

Manufacturing line: The allergen is handled on the production line.

DOMCA INNOVATIVE FOOD SOLUTIONS	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION
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DCM-ANTIOX: NATURAL ANTIOXIDANT

Description: DMC-Antiox is a nutraceutical based on extracts enriched in antioxidants that prevents cellular aging, strengthens the immune system and reduce the risk of degenerative diseases system.

How to use: 1 capsule per day, during the meal, with a large glass of water is recommended. It is not advised to take more than 3 capsules a day.

Composition: Antioxidant extracts. Loading agent: microcrystalline cellulose. Coating: Hydroxymethylpropylcellulose.

Packaging: Packages of 90 capsules. Each capsule contains 500 mg.

Labelling: Each package is clearly labelled with a product description, batch reference, production date, shelf-life and net weight.

Transport conditions:

- Non special conditions required.

Storage & shelf life:

- Protect from light, heat and humidity
- Shelf-life to be established

Recommendations:

- Do not exceed the recommended daily dose.
- Food supplements and nutraceuticals should not be used as a substitute for a balanced diet.
- Keep out of the reach of children.

Additional information:

- Suitable for vegans and vegetarians. Without allergens.

	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION
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REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS THAT THE PRODUCT MEETS

1. Good manufacturing practices and food safety

- REGULATION (EC) No 853/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs
- REGULATION (EC) No 2015/2283 2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2015 on the Novel Foods

2. Pesticides and contaminants

- Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 of 19 December 2006 setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs and amendments.
- Regulation (EC) No. 396/2005 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin and amending Council Directive 91/414/EEC and amendments.

3. Allergens / GMO / Ionising radiations

- Total absence of allergen substances according to REGULATION (EC) No 1169/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2011 on the provision of food information to consumers and amendments.
- In accordance with Regulations 1829/2003 (on labelling and traceability) and 1830/2003 (on genetically modified food) and their amending legislation of the European Parliament, this product does not contain any GMOs (including additives and flavourings), was not produced from any GMOs, was not manufactured using GMOs or products from GMOs and is not subject to the labelling obligation.
- In compliance with the Directive 1999/2/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 February 1999 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States concerning foods and food ingredients treated with ionising radiation, and the Directive 1999/3/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 February 1999 on the establishment of a Community list of foods and food ingredients treated with ionising radiation, this product is not treated with ionising radiation and does not contain any ingredient treated with ionising radiation.

 <small>andly bio</small>	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION
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MOISTURIZING BODY CREAM WITH ANTIOXIDANTS

Description: Our body moisturizer is a natural product with ecological ingredients. Made with zero waste, enriched with salts, clays, algae extract and antioxidants extracts. It is vegan, without parabens or nanomaterials. Hydration and protection against the cold.

High antiseptic and healing power. Repairs cracked skin.

Application: Dermocosmetic / Cosmetics

Specifications:

SENSORIC	Colour	Grey	
	Odour/Taste	Marine smell	
	Appearance	Cream paste	
		Min	Max
INCI	Oils (e.g., vegetable and/or mineral), waxes and fats(e.g., long chain alcohols)		30
	Silicones including volatile silicones (e.g. cyclopentasiloxane, dimethicone)		20
	Humectants (e.g., glycerin, propylene glycol, PEG)		20
	Thickeners (e.g., carbomer, xanthan gum)		12
	Ethanol (alcohol, alcohol denat.)		10
	Additional ingredients (e.g., vitamins, antioxidants, plant extracts)		10
	Bulking agents (e.g., tale, silica, nylon powder)		5
	UV Filters		5
	Emulsifying agents, anionic / amphoteric / non-ionic surfactants(e.g., PEG stearate, cetareth)		5
	Preservatives, antimicrobials		2
	Colorants		6
Parfum		1	
Aqua		100	
Formulation name	Cream, Lotion, gel for skin care.		

Packaging: Recycled Pet jars of 1 kg, 400ml, 200ml, 120ml and Recycled aluminum can of 120ml. 50ml and 15ml

Labelling: Each package is clearly labelled with a product description, batch reference, production date, shelf-life and net weight.

Transport conditions:

tankers with temperatures between 5° and 26°C.

Storage & shelf life:

- Best before 2 years

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.